

Gender and Development Programs in an Educational Institution: Views of Stakeholders

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Abstract

This phenomenological study understands the views of stakeholders in educational institutions regarding the implementation of the Gender and Development (GAD) program. Using a qualitative approach, six teachers from two public schools in Davao City were interviewed. Participants, selected through purposive sampling, had over five years of teaching experience and were not directly involved in the GAD program. Thematic analysis revealed several key findings. Despite efforts to promote gender equality, stakeholders noted significant challenges in the program's execution, particularly a lack of clarity in its implementation and communication. Teachers expressed concerns over insufficient training and resources, which hindered their ability to fully integrate GAD principles into their classrooms. While the commitment to addressing gender inequality was evident, the study highlighted a need for better coordination and more structured guidance from the program's focal persons. This study emphasises the necessity of enhancing the GAD program to ensure that its objectives align with practical, actionable outcomes within the educational system. By improving the implementation process and providing more precise direction, educational institutions can better contribute to gender inclusivity and equality. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of how GAD programs are viewed at the school level and offer an understanding of improving gender-related policies in educational settings.

Keywords: *GAD program, stakeholders, educational institutions, gender inequality, program implementation.*

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Introduction

Despite the numerous Gender and Development (GAD) programs implemented, whether these initiatives have genuinely impacted stakeholders remains unclear. Key questions arise: Have stakeholders experienced tangible benefits? Do these programs effectively address their needs? The views and experiences of those involved in GAD programs, particularly in educational institutions in Davao, must be considered to evaluate their effectiveness. While awareness of gender inequality has progress in

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addressing systemic biases remains slow. Unfair treatment persists due to ingrained biases, and significant barriers still hinder real progress (Llorens et al., 2021).

O'Connor (2019) further highlights that gender inequalities in higher education institutions (HEIs) remain a pressing issue. Women are underrepresented in senior leadership and full professorial roles despite ongoing efforts to improve representation. Men continue to dominate top-ranking positions in universities across America and Europe. To address these challenges, institutions must evaluate their GAD programs, tailor interventions to stakeholders' needs, and strengthen policies. Collaboration with external organisations and integrating gender initiatives into long-term strategies will enhance the effectiveness of these programs and advance gender equality.

Materials and Methods

This section comprised the materials and methods employed in qualitative-phenomenological research. Specifically covered the following aspects: research design, participants and sampling techniques, data collection process, data analysis procedures, the role of the researchers, rigour of the study, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The study employed a qualitative approach. As noted by Tenny et al. (2017), qualitative research allowed the researchers to conduct an in-depth examination of real-world issues by focusing on participants' experiences, addressing questions of "how" and "why." This approach's flexibility and open-ended nature were essential in providing deeper insights that could not be captured through quantifiable methods.

Qualitative research is centred on understanding the essence of phenomena and exploring the underlying reasons behind numerous observations, making it particularly valuable for assessing complex interventions. In gathering data, researchers utilised methods such as participant experiences and interviews. Notes were taken, and audio recordings were labeled and transcribed during the analysis phase. Some strategies were implemented to ensure the quality of the research, including the use of sampling techniques and the involvement of relevant stakeholders (Busetto et al., 2020).

Participants and Sampling Technique

Various sampling techniques have been applied across different fields, signifying the importance of selecting a suitable method for each study. In this research, the researchers used purposive sampling, as described by Bisht (2024), where participants were selected based on established criteria aligned with the study's objectives. Instead of utilising random selection, this method targeted individuals possessing relevant characteristics to provide focused insights. It was explicitly effective in qualitative research, where thorough and specific responses were essential.

This approach was well-suited for small populations and enriched the understanding of a particular subject. Participants were chosen by purposive sampling. The criteria were as follows: (1) they should be teachers who have taught for over five years of experience who were not directly involved with the GAD program; (2) they should be male and female faculty; and (3) they all faculty in two public education institutions.

Data Gathering Process

Specifically, the data collection in this study followed some steps implemented to ensure that participants provided sufficient information. Before collecting the data phase, the researchers established approvals from the participants, distributed consent forms, and organised in-depth interview procedures. During data collection, open-ended questions were used in face-to-face interviews, arranged during stakeholders' free periods and lasted approximately 1.5 hours. The results provided an understanding of stakeholders' views on implementing GAD programs. A validation process involving stakeholders was conducted to safeguard the instruments' effectiveness.

Data Analysis

The researchers conducted a thematic analysis in this study to determine, evaluate, and interpret the data. Caulfield (2022) described this technique as a technique for analysing qualitative data, mainly suited for examining texts, such as transcriptions, to identify recurring themes. Moreover, Braun and Clarke (2012) characterised it as an accessible, versatile approach that has gained popularity in qualitative data analysis. Similarly, Javadi and Zarea (2016) emphasised that a well-executed thematic analysis is valuable for reflecting on and clarifying reality. The thematic analysis's accuracy contributed to the findings' reliability and informativeness.

To provide context for the participants' experiences, the researchers reviewed their accounts multiple times to eliminate personal biases associated with the phenomenon. By exploring the experiences of others, the researchers uncovered new insights that had previously been unattainable. They identified statements within the accounts related to the phenomenon under study. By carefully examining these statements, the researchers revealed meanings relevant to the events.

Addressing personal assumptions was vital for aligning closely with the observed phenomenon. The researchers organised their interpretations into consistent themes across all accounts. This objective examination of the data remained free from biases that personal viewpoints might introduce. A detailed description of the phenomenon, including all identified themes, was provided and simplified into a clear one.

Role of the Researchers

The researchers served as the sole data collectors. According to the study, Wa-Mbaleka (2020) stated that data was collected through various methods in qualitative research, with the researcher frequently functioning as a key instrument. The expectations and ethical considerations associated with this role were carefully outlined. Emphasis was placed on the necessity of effectively understanding and rewarding this role to ensure rigor and credibility in the research.

Rigour of the study

The researchers were tasked with establishing the required protocols and procedures for the study. The criteria for ensuring the trustworthiness of the research encompassed credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Ahmed, 2024). Establishing the credibility of the study presented challenges for the researchers. According to Zorge (2023), ensuring the credibility of the study results was vital for aligning them with the data to reflect participants' experiences accurately. To validate credibility, the researchers conducted in-depth interviews to strengthen the reliability of the findings.

Transferability indicated that the results could be applicable in numerous contexts (Kyngas et al., 2020). The researchers reviewed the information gathered from the in-depth interviews, recognizing that future studies might modify the findings regarding stakeholder views on gender and development programs, even across different subjects and locations. To ensure dependability, the researchers maintained detailed records and implemented a clear record-keeping system. Finally, to achieve confirmability, the researchers demonstrated objectivity, safeguarding that the study's findings correctly represented participants' ideas and experiences rather than reflecting the researchers' biases, intentions, or interests. The researchers' ability to describe the significant and diverse challenges in the data collected from participants was essential for maintaining the study's authenticity.

To enhance the study's sense of confirmability, the researchers aimed to describe the methodologies in as much detail as possible. This consists of providing support for the qualitative approaches employed, outlining the literature search process, and detailing the coding themes as part of the methodological choices made in the study to reinforce its confirmability (Stanley & Robertson, 2024).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were carefully addressed during the study. Mirza et al. (2023) highlighted that researchers had responsibilities toward society, academic communities, their audience, and participants.

To ensure ethical compliance, established guidelines were rigorously followed. Key ethical factors, particularly in data gathering and analysis, included respecting participants, managing conflicts of interest, maintaining participant relationships, securing informed consent, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity, providing feedback to participants, ensuring the trustworthiness of the research, and addressing issues related to translation.

Given the rigour of qualitative research, adverse ethical situations often arise. The primary conflicts involved potential violations of confidentiality, disrespect for participant autonomy, risks of harm, ambiguity surrounding the roles of the researchers, and impasses within the Research Ethics Committee. Various conflicts can emerge in research settings. The recommended remedies included reflexivity, ethical mindfulness, ongoing consent, and self-awareness, foundational elements for addressing these ethical challenges.

Results

This section manifests the results from data analysis on the themes derived from the interviews with teachers.

Figure 1. Outlines the Views of Stakeholders on the Implementation of Gender and Development (GAD) Programs in Educational Institutions

Main Themes	Subthemes
Gender inequality is apparent and felt by some stakeholders.	Women are perceived as more privileged.
	There are double standards in language and treatment.
Implementation is insufficient and requires enhancement.	The implementation is unclear.
	Activities and projects are minimal.
There are significant gaps that need improvement.	More seminars and training are needed.
	Implementation needs to be proper and effective.
	There is a need for improvement.

Theme 1: Gender Inequality is Apparent and Felt by Some Stakeholders

Gender equality is critical in schools, influencing teacher interactions and the overall learning environment. By exploring teachers' views, important views into existing inequalities emerged. Feedback from teachers revealed that gender inequality was distinctly felt by some stakeholders, with women often perceived as having more privileges, leading to a sense of imbalance. Several teachers noted experiencing double standards in language and treatment, highlighting inconsistencies in how they were addressed within the educational setting.

The first sub-theme focused on teachers' views of the Gender and Development (GAD) program, particularly regarding the emphasis on women's privileges. Participants expressed concerns that the programs and seminars centred mainly on women's rights, with limited attention on men's issues. One participant remarked, "To protect themselves, people must be aware of their rights. Here in the Philippines, the focus tends to be more on women's rights because they are seen as weaker, while men's rights often go unaddressed" (P1). This response underscores the lack of discussion surrounding men's rights.

Another participant shared, "This is how we should follow things, so, ah, I should really do it this way, that we shouldn't just step on others, especially if you're in your married life" (P3).

It is also supplemented by the other participant, "Yes, yes, like that is what, like the disadvantage, right, is in our law, like there are many of what for women if that is being created" (P6). It further depicts the current situation about gender rights which appeared to have a minimal focus on men's privileges.

Another participant expressed sentiments, "We should thoroughly follow the rules and policy of school, number is haircut, I know you want ah, you want to look ah as like a woman is that what you are known for yourself but in just what I of, right there are women that has a boy cut but still allowed, still a woman, different hair, your haircut is short just like that then there is student that felt like being naked the moment while walking" (P4).

The second sub-theme emerged from double standards regarding language and treatment within the teaching environment. Some teachers have observed that their colleagues often feel uncomfortable with certain remarks.

Yes, ahmm, like I have noticed, just like but they just smile; they seem to be awkward, especially that there are our jokes, those green jokes that they are the target of; what is their protection for it? They like to laugh about it, but based on my observation, they felt awkward, they just laugh, but what must be done to stop it? It is like a problem like you noticed if done again what they will do like that (P1).

Furthermore, it is also elucidated, "So, aside from that, I've also applied it to our co-teachers, reminding them not to casually make remarks or jokes that might offend others, especially if someone is sensitive about their personality. Is it okay for a teacher to be like that and get upset easily? Is it acceptable to joke around with them like that?" (P 3). It is found that there are jokes from colleagues who are not careful in their utterances that have offended another person.

It is also reflected by the participant, "Why is it like that, or I always hear, oh you are supposed to be a teacher, it is too pitiful, too unfair for me as a teacher like I'm being a prisoner of the profession" (P4). It seems that there are gender stereotype experiences that limit the rights of gender, as well as the standards set that are not equally distributed to everybody.

Moreover, another participant shared, It's that we sometimes cannot avoid our community that is biased in judgment sometimes, though we observe somewhat if men commit like this, though not all men that like it is just okay to our society, but when it comes to women who commit such thing, it is not seen as to be a mistake from the view of others (P6).

Gender equality was critical in shaping school dynamics, where teachers pointed out clear imbalances. Women were often perceived as having more advantages, creating a sense of unequal treatment. Many teachers observed that the focus of the Gender and Development (GAD) program leaned heavily toward women's rights, leaving men's concerns largely unaddressed. This lack of balance led to feelings of exclusion among male teachers. Additionally, there were reports of double standards in how language and behaviour were managed, with some teachers feeling uncomfortable due to inappropriate jokes or remarks that went unchecked. Gender stereotypes further deepened these issues, as societal biases often allowed certain behaviours for men that women did not accept equally.

Theme 2: Implementation is Insufficient and Requires Enhancement

Stakeholders provided various views on the current state of the GAD program in educational institutions. Although the initiative addresses gender-related issues, its effectiveness hinges on proper implementation and support.

This theme highlighted that the program's implementation was inadequate and required enhancements. Participants noted a need for more training and prioritised activities related to GAD, resulting in insufficient coordination and unsustainable execution. Despite these challenges, the government has made efforts to raise awareness about the program's objectives.

The effectiveness of GAD implementations affects school employee satisfaction. Feedback indicated dissatisfaction due to unclear guidelines and policies.

I had a GAD seminar before where the teachers just sat and listened, and it didn't seem productive because it was one-sided. The resource person was already well-versed, so the listeners needed to absorb and understand the topic better. (P 3)

There are policies that we should evaluate to determine if they are gender-sensitive, especially regarding uniform policies for our students. I have observed that some schools practice these policies, so I wonder why we cannot implement them here. For instance, I saw a teacher whose uniform had a design typically meant for women but was cut for men. This shows that such practices are actually being followed elsewhere. (P4)

Yes, every day, what is being provided by GAD? Maybe it's just GAD is there, for me, I didn't really notice it. There was GAD, there were GAD elements, but I didn't realise I was involved in GAD. There was actually GAD implementation. (P 5)

Stakeholders revealed that while the Gender and Development (GAD) program aims to address gender concerns in schools, its implementation lacked proper and insufficient support. Teachers noted inadequate training, poor coordination, and a lack of prioritisation, leading to unsatisfactory results. Although the government raised awareness, unclear guidelines hindered the program's effectiveness. One teacher described GAD seminars as one-sided and unproductive, while another pointed out the absence of gender-sensitive policies, such as uniform regulations in other schools. Some teachers felt they needed to be made aware of their involvement in the program, reflecting its limited visibility and impact..

Theme 3: There are Significant Gaps that Need Improvement

The third theme emphasised areas needing improvement, as identified by stakeholders. Many aspects of the program require ongoing attention, and while the seminars were appreciated, participants requested additional GAD-related training.

The first sub-theme highlighted the desire for more seminars and training. Although attendees found value in the workshop, many felt it needed more.

Perhaps they should consider doing more. Instead of just the annual program, they might conduct the Gender and Development (GAD) program quarterly, if possible. (P1)

It was not just a one-time issue within a year. It is possible that the effectiveness of the program could vary depending on the budget available. (P4)

What I would like is for things to be clearer. I'm not sure, but perhaps the program could be more effective if it were not just a one-time event each year. It's possible that its effectiveness depends on the budget as well. (P5)

The second subtheme, reflecting teachers' views on the GAD program's execution, highlighted the necessity for more effective implementation. The main objective of any program is to ensure it is carried out efficiently and effectively, delivering substantial benefits to participants. Stakeholders observed that the management of the program needed to be improved, pointing out several areas needing attention.

Every year, we do not have a flowchart. What I suggest is that we should have a flowchart showing who our focal person is and who is involved in the program. For that kind of program, it is important to see who the focal person is. (P3).

The implementation was limited, and there were school policies that contradicted gender promotion. (P4)

I'm still thankful that our GAD seminar continues every year, but I've also noticed that there might be some shortcomings in the program. I haven't really felt its implementation here at the school. (P5)

The third theme that emerged was the need for improvement, which participants shared and expressed. Overall, implementing GAD initiatives in educational settings has yet to be fully effective. Various aspects, including program design, resource allocation, training, and engagement, require improvement to meet desired outcomes. Stakeholders emphasised the pressing need for enhancements.

It is important to have a record of accomplishments because this helps teachers understand what has happened, such as cases involving students or specific issues. This way, one can see if there is something already existing. For effective reporting, the focal person should hand over detailed reports and

accomplishments to the next focal person. This includes reports on expenditures and any awards given. This approach allows us to track the budget, understand how much was spent, and see if there are any remaining funds. This information helps us identify if there were any shortfalls or if the budget needs to be adjusted for future activities. (P3)

There were many programs that likely did not continue. There were also several factors that may have contributed to the lack of implementation, possibly including the coordinator's busy schedule. (P4)

This is what I understood about GAD, but I didn't really understand it before. I just accepted it as part of GAD, but I still didn't fully grasp what it was. What is supposed to happen? What is the role of the GAD Program? (P5)

Stakeholders conveyed that while the GAD program is valued, there is a clear call for significant enhancements. They noted the necessity for more sustainability and greater attention through additional seminars and training. Many asserted that single seminars are insufficient and advocated for increased frequency to boost effectiveness. Furthermore, teachers identified areas for improvement in the program's management and execution, pointing out issues like unclear responsibilities, insufficient resources, and conflicts with existing school policies. Suggestions for improvement included better documentation of achievements, meticulous budget oversight, and more consistent reporting from coordinators. Participants concurred that improved planning and support are critical for the program to fulfill its objectives.

Discussion

The feedback gathered from stakeholders offered valuable insights into implementing the Gender and Development (GAD) program in public educational institutions. This knowledge can empower them to engage more effectively in relevant activities and training. For example, Theme 1 highlighted gender inequality, with male stakeholders feeling excluded from GAD initiatives, leading to isolation and conflict with female colleagues. Some expressed concerns about biases favouring women, even when mistakes were made. These findings are consistent with previous research indicating that social isolation can heighten the risk of mental health issues (Loades et al., 2020).

Additionally, instances of gender-based unfair treatment were reported, reflecting the persistent influence of biases. Advocates have long argued that gender should not determine employment opportunities, with significant efforts supporting women's rights for decades, while advocacy for men's rights has been comparatively limited (Robinson et al., 2016). These findings suggest that despite efforts to promote inclusivity, certain biases remain entrenched, affecting both genders.

Theme 2 discussed the insufficient implementation of the GAD program and its impact on employee satisfaction. Stakeholders highlighted vague policies and guidelines, echoing Kyohairwe's (2019) assertion that proper training can enhance teachers' ability to integrate GAD concepts into their practice. This suggests that the GAD program's effectiveness is directly tied to its clarity and the support offered to educators.

Theme 3 emphasised the significant gaps in the program that require improvement. Participants expressed a desire for training specific to their roles in GAD, underscoring the importance of raising awareness. Kollmayer et al. (2020) also stressed that teachers have a crucial role in fostering gender equality, as their attitudes and practices influence student outcomes. The findings revealed that while efforts have been made, challenges such as insufficient funding, poor coordination, and unsustainable practices still need to be addressed, as Gil (2021) and Albaladejo (2016) noted.

In conclusion, although GAD programs exist, access and satisfaction levels vary, with many stakeholders questioning the program's goals and vision. Perigo and Mangila (2020) highlighted discrepancies between policy creation and implementation, pointing to stronger management support. Overall, the study suggests that while some progress has been made, significant work remains to ensure that GAD initiatives effectively address the needs of all stakeholders.

Conclusion

The study into gender equality in schools unveiled notable insights regarding the Gender and Development (GAD) programs from teachers' views. Many educators recognized significant gender inequality, perceiving women as having more privileges, which fostered a sense of imbalance. Discussions often centred on women's rights while neglecting men's issues, leading to feelings of exclusion among male teachers.

Furthermore, teachers reported discomfort due to double standards in language and treatment, particularly regarding inappropriate jokes that went unchecked. Although there were attempts to promote gender equality, implementation challenges persisted. Educators pointed to insufficient training, poor coordination, and inadequate prioritisation of gender concerns in school policies.

While some GAD seminars were valued, many felt that single events were insufficient, advocating for more frequent and impactful training opportunities. To address these issues, it was crucial to enhance the implementation of GAD initiatives by fostering ongoing education, improving program management, and updating policies to be more inclusive. Incorporating gender discussions into Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) meetings and all subjects could further promote stakeholder awareness. Future research focused on evaluating these programs to ensure their effectiveness and inclusivity.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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